

Low-CO₂ Development via Green Behaviour Mechanism and Strategy Research

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Abstract

Analysis of policy and mechanism of green behaviour, as well as the role of technology, in the relationship between policy and low carbon development in China was a primary goal of the study. Finance also played a significant role in the relationship, but only when technology was present. Finance plays a significant part in China's policy and mechanism for green behaviour and low carbon development. It was also revealed that the existence of technological variables in China's policy and mechanism of green behaviour and low carbon development has a beneficial impact on the interaction between policy and mechanism. As a result of the study, it is recommended that countries adjust to the urgent circumstances under the long-term goals for tackling climate change and to overcome the "Middle Income Trap" within innovation-driven and low carbon development

Keywords: *Technology innovation, Financial development, GDP growth, FMOLS, CO₂ emissions*

1. Introduction

The globe as a whole is at risk from climate change. In many cases, unintentional revelation can have disastrous consequences, such as the worldwide water and food crises (Patz, et al., 2020). Transportation management is the major focus of these initiatives that are mostly focused on low-carbon energy. In the development of low-carbon technology, people's behaviour has a significant impact (Liu et al., 2018). Insurance firms, in particular, are increasingly becoming engaged, which might lead to changes in the politics around global warming (Newell and Paterson, 1998). The impacts of urbanization, in particular, differ greatly among locations. Emission urbanization elasticity became negative in regions 2 and 3 over a certain point, and subsequent increases in urbanization had no effect on emissions (He et al., 2017). Both short and long term, population density, energy consumption, and economic expansion have statistically significant positive effects on CO₂ emissions (2015). Reducing greenhouse gas emissions necessitates the use of low-carbon technologies and the promotion of low-carbon growth. Emissions must be reduced without jeopardizing economic development in order to achieve a low carbon society (Ali et al., 2013). A low-carbon economic growth model is essential in the new era of national economic growth. As a country's economic lifeblood, the diverse sectors put great demands on the country's finite resources and its environment while providing its population with a wealth of material riches and aiding in rapid economic growth. Many governments feel that manufacturing is the greatest approach to build a low-carbon economy. Several countries have had some success with the implementation of low-carbon manufacturing. China has been referred to be a "manufacturing country" for many years. Low-carbon manufacturing hasn't been fully implemented yet. It is vital to perform a scientific and effective evaluation of China's manufacturing capability in terms of low-carbon manufacturing in order to better understand China's low-carbon manufacturing.

2. Literature Review

More and more studies have looked at how economic growth, energy consumption, technical advancement, population number, and the evolution of industrial structure all affect CO₂ emissions (Zhao et al., 2020). Sovereign risk is anticipated to rise dramatically as a result of CO₂ emissions, according to advanced countries (Chaudhry et al., 2020). Reducing carbon emissions can be achieved by renewable energy technology innovation, however fossil energy technological innovation is futile. Industrialized countries' policies and trends

on renewable energy and energy efficiency would reduce CO₂ emissions by 2030 if implemented... (Arroyo and Miguel, 2019). Different levels of financial development can also have an influence on the CO₂ emissions impact of financial development (Acheampong, 2019). The ability to meet the energy trilemma by providing enough clean energy to rural and urban regions rests heavily on the success of RE technology R&D. (Ebhotu and Jen, 2020). Old enterprises may be upgraded and optimised, and carbon emissions can be reduced, as a result of better allocation of scarce resources when financial development improves. For further information, please see the reference below. Climate change and low-carbon innovation are intertwined because of environmental regulations (Wang et al., 2020). Low-carbon innovation takes happen; however, it does not explain the variance in the development of various low-carbon innovation forms (Leonidou and Leonidou, 2011). Carbon emissions can foster a wide variety of low-carbon innovation types. There has been a lack of research on the human characteristics that assist low-carbon innovation (Paramati et al. 2020). Using renewable energy, environmental taxes, and human capital to reduce CO₂ emissions have been identified. In both the short and long term, GDP expansion has a detrimental effect on the environment (Ahmad et al., 2020). Environmental awareness has a dual effect on the development of low-carbon technology. With the use of technical patents, companies may attract finance while also employing cutting-edge technology to reduce the effects of global warming (Lingyan et al., 2021). Climate change is influenced by both technological improvement and financial development (Shoaib et al., 2020). A critical component of characterizing the fundamental environmental factors is an endogenous growth model that integrates the moderating effects of technological progress (Rafique et al., 2020). Various economic initiatives aimed at promoting economic growth have the unintended consequence of hurting the environment and exacerbating climate change (Ozturk et al., 2020). Finance, global warming, and an ever-increasing need for energy are all key drivers of environmental concern (He et al., 2021). As a result of climate change, it is increasingly difficult for growing countries to achieve long-term economic growth (Zameer et al., 2020). Financial innovation-driven economic growth has the potential to hasten global warming (Bekhet et al., 2017). Economic growth is the primary driver of climate change, but it also contributes to environmental degradation. Developmental economies lack the financial policies and infrastructure of developed economies (Shahzad et al., 2021). Through the use of efficient technological sources, it is also vital to consider the impact of financial development on climate change (Shoaib et al., 2020). Climate change poses a severe threat to the long-term viability of global ecosystems and human civilization (Chu et al., 2021). They found that Guangdong's carbon emissions were reduced by 10% using a synthetic control approach, which is consistent with the findings of Yu and colleagues (2019). Industrial upgrading, energy efficiency, and technological advancement are just a few of the ways manufacturing companies may reduce their carbon emissions (Song et al., 2020). Polluting industries' resources may gradually transfer to green industries, creating a cluster of green industries as a result of both government support and the effects of industrial migration (Sun et al., 2021). The study employed an FMOLS estimation technique to examine the detrimental impact of energy use on the EF of the study participants.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Financial development, trade, technical advancements, green behaviour regulatory mechanisms, and low-CO₂ emissions organizational quality have all been studied extensively in relation to economic growth. More study is needed on these topics, though. Here, we see how independent and linked variables interact in Figure 1.

Figure.1. Theoretical framework of dependent and independent variables

3.2 Econometrics Description

As a proponent of economic growth, the course includes late twentieth-century content. One-equation methods were used to calculate the models (Redmond and Nasir, 2020).

$$CO_2 = f(FD, GDP, EXP, IMP, FD, RE, IQV)$$

Reduced carbon emissions are made possible in part by the expansion of green financing, which has four key features. According to a research published in Environmental Science & Technological Innovation (TI) and Exports (EXP), the gross domestic product GDP, carbon dioxide (CO₂) gas is a key contributor to environmental contamination. In China's efforts to reduce pollution, renewable energy sources (RE) play an important role. How well an organization is run may be gauged by looking at how well it controls corruption, regulates its own operations, enforces the law, and holds itself and its members of leadership accountable (Redmond and Nasir, 2020).

3.3 Data Collection Sources

Due to a lack of available data, the analysis provides data for China from 1985 to 2020. Following the literature, a collection of possible influences on human development has been developed and confirmed. The study provides an overview of the factors and data sources as follows.

Variables Definition and Sources

Variables	Definition	Source
<i>lnGDP</i>	The logarithm of GDP per capita	WB
<i>lnCO₂</i>	First major contributor of environmental pollution	UNDP
<i>lnEXP</i>	Exports	IMF
<i>lnFD</i>	Financial Development	IMF
<i>lnES</i>	Renewal Energy	WDI

WDI: World Development Indicator; <https://datacatalog.worldbank.org.com>; UNDP: United Nation Development Program <http://hdr.undp.org.com>; IMF: International Monetary Fund; <https://data.imf.org.com>

As compared to previous studies, the one discloses the components of each dimension of Financial Development (FD). Sharia governance quality and risk management measures to protect stakeholders and the quantitative development of international financial institutions and markets (Quantitative) are some of the key contemporary issues that were taken into consideration when selecting different components of the Indicator

(Quantitative), The study used data from the Shanghai Stock Market, China Statistical Yearbook, the CSMAR Database, and the Shenzhen stock market to compile information on financial development (FD) and economic growth (GDP) for 380 enterprises. Environmental sustainability (ES), carbon emissions (CO₂), technological innovation (TI), as well as energy sources are all collected in China's Statistical Yearbooks for Environment, Science & Technology, and Energy. The equation in a linear form as;

$$CO_{2t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 FD_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 EXP_t + \beta_4 TI_t + \beta_5 ES_t + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

In equation-2, β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 and β_5 are the parameters of FD, GDP, EXP, TI and ES respectively, while t symbolizes the studied country. Also, α_0 is the constant term, while μ_t represents the stochastic error term, natural logarithm was taken on both sides of equation-2 resulting in the ensuing specification;

$$\ln CO_{2t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln FD_t + \beta_2 \ln GDP_t + \beta_3 \ln EXP_t + \beta_4 \ln TI_t + \beta_5 \ln ES_t + \mu_t \quad (3)$$

Where $\ln CO_2$, $\ln FD$, $\ln GDP$, $\ln EXP$, $\ln TI$ and $\ln ES$ are the log conversions of the output and the input variables correspondingly.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table-1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. The table shows that CO₂ emissions have the lowest average value. Data from FD and ES have huge standard deviations, making it difficult to compare their mean values with those from CO₂ and FD, which are near to their mean values despite their enormous standard deviations. Similarly, the LnCO₂ concentration is seen to be skewed to the right. The left side of the variable distribution is strongly skewed, whereas the right side is longer tailed on the left side of the distribution

Table.1. Descriptive statistics of variables

Statistic	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	VIF	Tolerance (4/VIF)
lnCO ₂	-1.433	-1.984	-0.374	-1.774	0.58	0.434	2.473	-	-
lnFD	0.477	0.647	0.377	0.404	0.72	-0.044	2.437	1.74	0.433
lnGDP	0.342	0.473	1.447	-1.074	1.332	-0.447	1.407	3.277	0.433
lnTI	1.343	1.564	1.043	2.737	0.474	-0.433	3.474	2.437	0.454
lnEXP	0.747	0.674	1.234	0.347	0.447	-0.343	1.707	1.344	0.747
lnES	1.477	1.267	2.044	0.022	1.703	-4.443	4.443	1.544	0.764

To put it another way, their data was more likely to be located on the right side of the distribution and had a longer left tail than the other factors.

4.2 Unit Root Tests

The findings of Levin, Lin, and Chu (2002), Fisher-type tests employing ADF and PP tests, as well as tests for panel unit root stationarity, can be seen in Table 2. According to the findings, all variables are ordered I when analysed at a significance level of 0.01. (1). Levin, Lin, and Chu (2002), Fisher-type testing utilising ADF and PP tests, and panel unit root tests employing three different types of stationarity tests all yielded interesting findings. It's possible that some variables of order are significant at the 0.01% level I(1).

Table.2. Panel Unit Root tests

Variables	Method	Level		first difference	
		Statistic	Prob	Statistic	Prob
lnGDP	Levin, Lin & Chu	-24.502	(0.000*)	-19.54	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	202.57	(0.037**)	374.652	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	243.56	(0.000*)	246.724	(0.000*)
lnCO ₂	Levin, Lin & Chu	4.419	0.0001*	-6.657	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	64.64	-0.647	56.247	-0.372
	PP - Fisher	57.702	(0.02**)	242.606	(0.002*)
lnEXP	Levin, Lin & Chu	-4.545	(0.000*)	-7.57	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	72.572	(0.047**)	194.746	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	242.542	(0.002*)	195.745	(0.000*)
lnFD	Levin, Lin & Chu	-6.456	(0.000*)	-37.256	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	54.547	-0.192	200.435	(0.024**)
	PP - Fisher	215.037	(0.002*)	372.424	(0.000*)
lnES	Levin, Lin & Chu	-25.702	(0.000*)	-19.745	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	376.274	(0.000*)	195.215	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	243.427	(0.000*)	372.424	(0.000*)
IQV1	Levin, Lin & Chu	-20.575	(0.000*)	-20.064	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	240.604	(0.002*)	192.074	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	242.702	(0.000*)	246.576	(0.000*)
IQV2	Levin, Lin & Chu	-20.537	(0.000*)	-40.615	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	240.52	(0.002*)	247.024	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	174.243	(0.000*)	196.24	(0.000*)
IQV3	Levin, Lin & Chu	-20.427	(0.000*)	-27.252	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	56.434	(0.057***)	377.45	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	215.404	(0.000*)	243.45	(0.000*)
IQV4	Levin, Lin & Chu	-37.645	(0.000*)	-37.246	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	246.657	(0.000*)	252.724	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	250.52	(0.000*)	195.196	(0.000*)
IQV5	Levin, Lin & Chu	-19.028	(0.000*)	-19.076	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	47.92	(0.057***)	265.028	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	178.027	(0.000*)	187.892	(0.000*)
IQV6	Levin, Lin & Chu	-27.902	(0.000*)	-233.782	(0.000*)
	ADF - Fisher	195.078	(0.000*)	72.092	(0.000*)
	PP - Fisher	234.089	(0.000*)	205.757	(0.000*)

Note: P-value in parentheses, *, **, and *** show significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.
 Source: Authors' estimations.

Economic growth may be influenced either directly or indirectly by the quality of an organisation. A country's level of economic development affects the impact of several factors, including organisational quality and trade openness, on economic growth. After separating their 60-country panel data set into World Bank income categories, Law et al. (2013) discovered a strong connection between development and organisational quality.

4.3 Estimation of FMOLS Model

Various models have been developed to investigate the impact of various factors on HDI. FMOLS and DOLS findings are shown in the top and bottom parts of the tables, respectively, so that the results of the initial estimate may be compared. Table 3 investigates how the different characteristics of organizational quality, oil rents, and their interactions on one other affect the human development index.

Table.3. Results of estimating the FMOLS model indicators

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9
lnGDP	7.642	7.534	7.656	6.907	7.276	7.626	6.953	7.146	7.644
	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)
lnFD	2.267	2.262	2.276	2.146	2.427	2.23	2.274	2.064	2.256
	(0.027**)	(0.023**)	(0.023**)	(0.023**)	(0.001*)	(0.026**)	(0.027**)	(0.027**)	(0.007*)
lnES	-0.023	-0.023	-0.023	-0.023	-0.027	-0.023	-0.027	-0.007	-0.023

	(0.004*)	(0.001*)	(0.004*)	(0.002*)	(0.003*)	(0.002*)	(0.007*)	-0.253	(0.053****)
IQV2		-0.053							
		-0.724							
IQV2			0.242						
			-0.723						
IQV4				-2.272					
				(0.04**)					
IQV4					2.702				
					(0.006*)				
IQV4						-0.47			
						-0.467			
IQV6							0.627		
							(0.056***)		
Tech (IQV4+IQV4)								-0.042	-0.042
								(0.002*)	(0.002*)
Rent (IQV6+IQV6)								0.623	
								(0.027**)	
R ²									0.023
									(0.044**)
R ²	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789

It has been decided to input each of the several organizational quality variables in a separate model because of the possibility of collinearity. The coefficient of GDP logarithm estimation findings show that the variable has a favourable impact on the human development index. A positive coefficient is important in all equations, and the coefficient's value is somewhere around zero (9.01). Human development index can rise by 8 to 9 units for every 1% growth in GDP. The logarithmic coefficient of government spending is also substantial and positive. In all models, the openness variable has a negative coefficient. According to the findings, each 0.03-percentage-point rise in the GDP share of international trade (total exports minus total imports) might lead to a little drop in GDP.

4.4 Estimation of DOLS Model

Both FMOLS and DOLS models predict similar coefficients for the three variables in question. Estimating IQ1 through IQ6 (the six measures of organizational quality) yields similar findings as well. The coefficients of IQ3, IQ4, and IQ6 are significant in the FMOLS model.

Table.4. Results of estimating the DOLS model indicators

Variables	Model 10	Model 11	Model 12	Model 13	Model 14	Model 15	Model 16	Model 17	Model 18
lnGDP	7.13	7.137	7.08	8.748	8.637	7.248	7.247	7.424	8.813
	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)
lnFD	2.063	2.074	2.132	2.274	2.063	2.242	2.07	0.694	2.284
	(0.027**)	(0.027**)	(0.027**)	(0.02*)	(0.028**)	(0.024**)	(0.027**)	(0.027**)	(0.004*)
lnES	-0.024	-0.024	-0.024	-0.024	-0.013	-0.024	-0.013	-0.013	-0.024
	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.002*)	(0.00*)	(0.002*)	(0.07***)	(0.028**)
IQV1		0.042							
		-0.748							
IQV2			0.27						
			-0.634						
				-2.028					

				(0.074***)					
IQV3					2.207				
					(0.07***)				
IQV4						-0.288			
						-0.469			
							0.474		
IQV5								-0.044	-0.044
								(0.00*)	(0.00*)
Tech (IQV2+IQV3)								0.442	
								(0.07***)	
Rent (IQV4+IQV5)									0.007
									(0.027**)
R2	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789

However, in the DOLS model, only IQ3 and IQ4 are found to be statistically significant. There are basically no differences between the model and the FMOLS one. Both the total of IQ4 and the sum of IQ6 had a favourable influence on the human development index in models 8 and 17 of the study. The negative and significant value of -0.01 represents the resource rent coefficient. IQ4 and IQ6 also have a positive and substantial total coefficient. Organizational quality has been studied in models 9 and 18 to see how it affects the efficacy of resource rents. For the, the model includes the term "interaction RENT" (IQ4+IQ6). There is a relationship between FD and resource rent in models 9 and 18 as seen in the following table.

4.5 Estimations of FMOLS model for the two variables

In Table 5, after looking at the effects of resource rents and organizational quality, the Finance Development (FD) and its four aspects are examined in relation to HDI. Models 19 and 24 both have a positive and statistically significant FD coefficient.

Table.5. The results in the FMOLS model for the two variables

Variables	Model 19	Model 20	Model 21	Model 22	Model 23
lnGDP	7.631 (0.00*)	7.158 (0.00*)	7.731 (0.001*)	7.467 (0.00*)	7.164 (0.00*)
lnFD	1.461 (0.007*)	1.031 (0.031**)	1.167 (0.071***)	1.2631 (0.007*)	1.311 (0.031**)
EXP	-0.031 (0.031**)	-0.007 -0.61	-0.031 (0.058***)	-0.031 (0.0631**)	-0.031 (0.07***)
Rent (IQV5+IQV6)	0.031 (0.077***)	0.014 (0.077***)	0.016 (0.014**)	0.031 (0.001*)	0.031 (0.004*)
FD	0.016 (0.007*)				
ES		0.0631 (0.00*)			
CSR			0.007 -0.631		
IQV				0.031 -0.311	
KNO					0.006 -0.467
R ²	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789

Note: P-Value in parentheses, *, **, and *** show significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.

Source: Authors' estimations.

However, it is impossible to witness such beneficial and noticeable consequences in all of its facets. EXP has a favourable influence on GDP growth, while the other factors are minor, according to FMOLS model results. Financial development (FD), despite its positive and considerable consequences on CO2 emissions, will be examined in terms of environmental pollution in our assessment.

4.6 Estimation of DOLS model for the two variables

Green finance may be made more transparent by studying the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on China's environmental damage. The data in the previous table shows that the good benefits of financial development cannot be separated. In addition, we looked at the influence of each of the six dimensions that make up FD in Table-6.

Table.6. The results in the DOLS model for the two variables

Variables	Model 24	Model 25	Model 26	Model 27	Model 28
lnGDP	6.963	9.269	9.406	9.136	6.957
	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)
lnFD	1.126	1.069	1.3	1.326	1.326
	(0.004*)	(0.004*)	(0.004*)	(0.009*)	(0.004*)
EXP	-0.032	-0.011	-0.013	-0.011	-0.011
	(0.004*)	(0.013**)	(0.00*)	(0.001*)	(0.001*)
Rent (IQV6+IQV7)	0.009	0.001	0.01	0.01	0.01
	(0.057***)	-0.673	(0.032**)	(0.031**)	(0.014**)
FD	0.011				
	(0.003*)				
ES		0.043			
		(0.00*)			
CSR			0.003		
			-0.414		
IQV				0.016	
				(0.069***)	
KNO					0.006
					-0.106
R ²	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789

Note: P-Value in parentheses, *, **, and *** show significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.

Source: Authors' estimations.

Models 29 and 38 indicate that the coefficient of FD in both estimating approaches is positive and significant. The FMOLS model has a coefficient value of 7.717, whereas the DOLS model has a coefficient value of 6.667. FMOLS model only has a substantial EXP coefficient and a close-to-significant RE and IQV coefficient.

4.7 Financial Development Impact on GDP growth

There are many reasons to believe that FD is more significant than GDP, despite the fact that the type of analysis takes a substantial quantity of data to discriminate between financial and non-financial performance in several aspects. Table 7 summarizes the results.

Table.7. The results of the coefficient of FD of FMOLS Models

Variables	Model 29	Model 30	Model 31	Model 32	Model 33	Model 34	Model 35	Model 36	Model 37
lnGDP	7.994	7.895	7.436	7.918	8.443	7.448	7.798	7.834	9.113
	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	-0.119	(0.00*)	(0.002*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)
lnFD	1.257	1.38	2.327	1.439	2.297	1.358	1.442	1.31	0.787
	(0.011**)	(0.013**)	-0.344	(0.008*)	(0.096***)	(0.006*)	(0.005*)	(0.009*)	-0.15
EXP	-0.02	-0.022	-0.02	-0.023	-0.016	-0.018	-0.021	-0.015	-0.008
	(0.004*)	(0.003*)	-0.271	(0.002*)	-0.209	(0.008*)	(0.003*)	(0.048**)	-0.305
Rent (IQV5+IQV6)	0.01	0.011	0.026	0.01	0.024	0.01	0.012	0.008	0.025
	(0.098***)	(0.094***)	-0.231	-0.134	(0.061**)	-0.109	(0.055**)	-0.212	(0.001*)
FD	7.717								
	(0.014**)								
ES		2.352							
		-0.226							
IQV1			-0.283						
			-0.861						
IQV2				3.341					
				-0.145					
IQV3					1.403				
					-0.322				
IQV4						9.256			
						(0.009*)			
IQV5							2.385		
							(0.071****)		
IQV6								7.562	
								-0.117	
R ²	0.789	0.789	0.998	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789

The results of the coefficient of FD of DOLS Models

Variables	Model 38	Model 39	Model 40	Model 41	Model 42	Model 43	Model 44	Model 45	Model 46
lnGDP	9.274	9.595	9.537	9.552	9.551	7.625	9.129	9.159	9.034
	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)
lnFD	1.294	1.145	1.405	1.15	1.157	1.109	1.162	1.174	1.157
	(0.009*)	(0.007*)	(0.005*)	(0.005*)	(0.005*)	(0.007*)	(0.005*)	(0.009*)	(0.005*)
EXP	-0.034	-0.014	-0.014	-0.015	-0.034	-0.034	-0.015	-0.029	-0.014
	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.00*)	(0.001*)	(0.001*)	(0.00*)	(0.034**)	(0.00*)
Rent (IQV4+IQV5)	0.009	0.01	0.01	0.009	0.009	0.01	0.034	0.007	0.01
	(0.051**)	(0.041**)	(0.037**)	(0.052****)	(0.043**)	(0.041**)	(0.029**)	-0.154	(0.034**)
FD	7.627								
	(0.047**)								
ES		1.079							
		-0.174							
IQV1			-0.519						
			-0.377						
IQV2				4.737					
				(0.057**)					
IQV3					1.541				
					-0.159				
IQV4						9.534			
						(0.014**)			
IQV5							1.627		
							-0.174		
IQV6								10.079	

								(0.029**)	
R ²	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789	0.789

P-Value in parentheses, *, **, and *** show significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively

Source: Authors' estimations.

Both the asymmetric FMOLS diagnostic statistics and DOLS model's symmetric diagnostic statistics are quite comparable. In other words, cointegration is there, but there is no problem with autocorrelation, and the model is appropriately defined, and an adjusted R2 of 0.789 indicates a satisfactory match. In terms of economic growth, exports are more important than imports. Growth may be raised only by international trading, which has long and short-term benefits for both rich and developing nations, according to a model that does not include aggregate scale effects or technology transfer.

4.8 Discussion

Adverse consumption circumstances produce major environmental concerns in China, according to the "Environmental Incentive Guide," published by the World Resources Institute. We haven't reached the end of ecological consumption as a notion. According to Betty, a foreign expert, harming the environment may be done by using resources and purchasing recyclable items, for example. Customers are unable to recognize greener items (apart from cleaning products) despite their preference for greener brands, according to Carlson (2019). They also regard the existing product promotion to be irrelevant and uninteresting. Ecological concern, according to Yue et al. (2021), has a favourable effect on green purchasing intention and plays a partly mediatory function in the interaction between environmental responsibility and green consumption intention. When environmental responsibility, environmental concern, and green consumption intention are all considered together, price sensitivity acts as a negative moderation. In light of our original theoretical model and the research cited, we stress the significance of examining both the material and social elements of chronic environmental contamination experience (Sullivan et al., 2021). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) estimates that 80 percent of global greenhouse gas emissions are a result of combustion (IPCC, 2007). Allowing the use of renewable energy sources implies that "energy distribution services boost productivity, efficiency, and efficiency.". As a rule, renewable energy licenses are more expensive than traditional means of generating electricity. Climate change and adaptation have shifted in recent years to emphasize the strategies of poor countries.

5. Conclusions

Analysis of policy and mechanism of green behaviour, as well as the role of technology, in the relationship between policy and low carbon development in China was a primary goal of the study. Finance also played a significant role in the relationship, but only when technology was present. A representative sample of 400 people was used to acquire the data, which was drawn from a dataset covering China from 1980 through 2020. FMOLS techniques were used to analyse the data in the study, and the findings were computed. Some control factors, such as GDP per capita and international commerce or trade openness, have favourable influence on FMOLS and DOLS model estimates. While trade openness has a detrimental impact on China's environmental pollution, it also has a bad impact on the country's CO2 emissions, which directly contribute to pollution. When the share of resource revenues to GDP (resource rent) rises, pollution increases. In the event that resource income does indeed contribute to a rise in GDP per capita and government spending, then both of these independent factors might potentially lead to an increase in environmental degradation. According to the findings, when financial development increases, it has a favourable impact on both economic growth and pollution levels. Quantitative progress and an understanding of good governance are two of FD's four pillars. Green finance's growth, expansion, and depth may be seen through the quantitative development index, which examines aspects such as growth expansion and depth, market performance, and financial stability. It also

shows that the financial development industry's health is strongly linked to infrastructure development, which in turn has a favourable impact on international commerce.

5.1 Future Suggestions

To sum up, it's time to embrace technological breakthroughs that can help reduce environmental pollution. In the investigation, one of the biggest drawbacks is the difficulty in obtaining data. Some of the variables lacked sufficient historical data. By employing information interjection and extrapolation, the dataset's missing data is finally filled in. Consequently, future comparative studies may be necessary to ensure the validity of the analysis's conclusions. Research on technology shocks can be expanded by including digitalization into the present model. Future studies might test the validity of the study's findings by comparing it to other indexes of income inequality. Finally, the link between China's population density, environmental pollution, income disparity, and economic growth is examined.

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